

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Self-Supervised Neural Networks for Precoding in MIMO Rate Splitting Multiple Access Systems

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ABSTRACT The use of machine learning (ML) tools to address the challenges posed in next generation of wireless communication systems has been gaining significant momentum. In this paper, we investigate the use of self-supervised data-driven schemes for precoder optimization in the downlink of a Multiple-Input Multiple-Output (MIMO) Rate Splitting Multiple Access (RSMA) system. Specifically, we propose two architectures based on Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) respectively, and analyze their achievable sum-rate performance in the underloaded and critically-loaded regime as the system scales up. The intention is to explore several alternatives to conventional iterative precoding benchmarks like Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) which are computationally intensive algorithms. We evaluate the different precoding policies learnt by the neural network architectures by closely studying the respective radiation patterns. Complementarily, we compare their complexity in terms of the number of trainable parameters and computation time. We also extend the evaluation to non-linear channels in RSMA settings. The study dictates that GNN-based scheme offers an interesting performance-complexity and scalability trade-off.

INDEX TERMS Graph neural network, deep learning, RSMA, precoding, non-linearity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Next Generation Multiple Access (NGMA) schemes play a vital role in using resources efficiently to cater to the upcoming 6G era of multi-user systems with varying requirements. Interference management among these users becomes extremely important in the next generation of wireless systems as the number of devices in the network is expected to increase dramatically [1]. In Non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA), multiple users share the same time and frequency resources, but are differentiated based on power levels [2]. The strong user must decode and cancel all the weaker user signals prior to decoding its own signal. This means that the interference is fully decoded at the receivers. Alternatively, Rate Splitting Multiple Access

(RSMA) has been pointed out as a unifying framework of existing MA schemes - Orthogonal Multiple Access (OMA), Space Division Multiple Access (SDMA) and NOMA [3]. RSMA is based on smart combination of transmit-side and receive-side interference cancellation to manage multi-user interference [4]. The notion behind RSMA is to split user messages into common and private parts, thus enabling the capability of partially decoding interference and partially treating the interference as noise [5]. RSMA has been shown to outperform NOMA [3], [6] [7] in multi-input single-output (MISO) settings, both in terms of system capacity and efficient use of Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC) steps. The superiority of RSMA over NOMA in multi-input multi-output (MIMO) configurations is discussed in [8]. RSMA enhances the benefits of MU-MIMO by achieving higher data rates and better interference management, especially when users are located closer and/or

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under imperfect Channel State Information at Transmitter (CSIT) [4].

Due to the RSMA ability of interference management technique where it partially decodes interference and partially treats the inter-user interference as noise, RSMA has received much attention for 6G [4], [9]. All these observations have led to the recommendation of 3GPP RAN to consider a study item on RSMA in Rel-19, which was outlined in 3GPP TSG RAN Rel-19 workshop [10], [11]. Furthermore, ETSI has established an Industry Specification Group (ISG) on Multiple Access Technologies (ETSI ISG MAT) [12]. This ISG is aimed to investigate downlink multi-user multiple access techniques for the physical layer of the 6G radio interface to enhance transmission efficiency (e.g., spectrum efficiency, power consumption, latency, user fairness, etc.) for unicast-only delivery, and joint broadcast/multicast and unicast delivery. The candidate downlink Multiple Access Techniques in the scope are OMA, SDMA, NOMA and RSMA, with the focus of the ISG on RSMA.

The simplest and most practical RSMA scheme is 1-layer Rate Splitting (RS), which is the basic building block of almost all existing RSMA schemes. It involves transmission of common stream which is built from parts of messages of all the users, and individual private streams (details in Section II). At the receiver, RSMA involves decoding of common message symbols, followed by SIC and decoding of individual private messages. Precoder optimization plays an important role in interference management of the common and private streams in the system. A number of studies [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18] have looked into the beamforming design for various system settings.

The widely adopted Weighted Minimum Mean Square Error (WMMSE) algorithm is applied in [6] and [14] to obtain the precoders in RSMA system. In [6], the RSMA sum-rate maximization problem is formulated as a convex Quadratically Constrained Quadratic Problem (QCQP). At each iteration, an Alternate Optimization (AO) algorithm is applied to update a set of scalar equalizers and user weights to optimize the precoders. As an extension to the above method, [13] introduces Sampled Average Approximation (SAA)-WMMSE method under known CSIT and CSIT error distribution. The application of the above variations of WMMSE is computationally intensive as the number of transmit antennas and users in the system increases. Other schemes include the application of algorithms such as successive convex approximation (SCA) [6] and semi-definite relaxation (SDR) [17], [19]. All the above approaches are implemented using iterative-based solvers (e.g., CVX toolbox), whose computational complexity becomes intensive as the system size scales up. Alternatively, sub-optimal schemes involve the use of zero-forcing (ZF) for obtaining the private precoders, along with the use of the eigenvector associated to largest eigenvalue obtained for the common stream [20], [21], [22]. However, the system capacity achieved is not satisfactory, especially in large RSMA settings which are characterized by high number of transmit antennas and/or number of users.

A number of works can be found in the literatures [23], [24], and [25] that explore the application of Deep Learning (DL) to enhance the WMMSE algorithm. Specific to RSMA scenario, the authors in [25] intentionally overfit a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) to learn the precoders of WMMSE algorithm for one channel realization and use it as a starting reference for subsequent channels, inspired by meta-learning based precoder design. In [26], deep convolutional neural networks (CNN) are used in a supervised manner to learn the linear precoders for rate splitting of aerial computing networks. The above methods require labeled datasets (i.e., instances of precoders from the WMMSE scheme) to train the neural networks in a supervised manner. Acquiring such large WMMSE precoder labels is time consuming and inefficient, especially for large RSMA settings. This can be completely eliminated by training the system in a self-supervised manner [23], [27]. This is accomplished by defining a customized loss function to train the neural networks. The loss function is only dependent on the *channel response* instead of using precoder labels from the computationally intensive WMMSE precoding scheme. Among self-supervised approaches, [27] looks into the use of transformers to perform precoder optimization in an end-to-end RSMA setting with analog and digital beamforming networks.

The most recent works on deep-unfolding methods for beamforming design in RSMA settings [28], [29], [30] offer better interpretability of the WMMSE algorithm, but do not eliminate the need for labeled datasets, i.e., precoder labels for RSMA settings. Specifically, [28] outlines a training process that involves two stages. The first stage involves supervised training of the model with labels from fractional programming hyperplane fixed point iteration (FP-HFPI). The second stage involves unsupervised learning with a loss function of negative sum-rate depending on the precoder values output from the L-th unfolded iteration. In [29], the deep unfolding precoding network makes use of transformer modules with 6 layers of MLP to first extract features from CSIT and then to output the precoders values. The computational complexity from the self-attention layers in Transformer is significantly higher compared to our proposed GNN model. In [30], gradient descent has been applied to convert WMMSE algorithm into a neural network model. The input of the model is the CSIT and user weight vector, the model parameters are the common and private precoder values, the output of the model is weighted mean squared error (WMSE). The goal of reducing the WMSE is achieved with lesser number of iterations and the sum-rate achieved is identical to WMMSE benchmark.

Another class of ML methods include the use of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to optimize power allocation in RSMA system [31], [32], [33]. The RSMA power allocation problem is formulated as a Markov Decision Process (MDP) and various RL algorithms are used to solve the task. In [32], DRL is applied for finding the optimal power allocation in RSMA wireless network with average sum-rate superior to SDMA. The authors in [33] explore

the use of multi-agent deep deterministic policy gradient in a scenario with 2 base stations serving 2 users. The actor network outputs a precoding matrix based on CSIT. For the MISO case, the DRL reaches convergence after 500 episodes, with 1000 time steps each. Although DRL is a robust learning solution, it has been shown that the number of training episodes increases substantially as the number of antennas at transmitter and receiver increases. The increase in number of antennas demands more training to optimize the RL model, without guarantee of stable convergence.

It is also of utmost importance to investigate the impact of non-linearities on precoding policies in the end-to-end communications channel. This can be in the form of hardware impairments like phase noise due to quantization, I/Q imbalance, or non-linearities in the power amplifiers of MIMO systems. For instance, [34] focuses on distortion-aware linear precoding for MISO downlink, while [35] shows the superiority of GNN over MLP for MIMO precoding.

A. CONTRIBUTIONS

This paper investigates the use of Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and Multi-layer Perceptron (MLP) for RSMA precoder optimization. The precoder matrix is permutation equivariant with the channel matrix, which means that if there is a change in the order of transmit antennas and users in channel matrix, the order of the precoding vectors also changes/permutates accordingly [35]. A GNN architecture exhibits permutation equivariance property [36], i.e., the output of the GNN reflects any permutation in the ordering of the input nodes/features. If the nodes (which represent the transmit antennas and users) are reordered, the output of the GNN will change correspondingly. This property is not exhibited by MLP which simply takes a row vector as input. Thus, GNN is a suitable architecture that can be applied for the precoding task. The use of GNN offers scalable solutions (e.g., reduced number of trainable parameters, number of operations) for MIMO precoder optimization [23], [37]. For this reason, we extend the application of GNN for RSMA beamforming and compare its performance to MLPs and other existing benchmarks.

In the considered framework, the neural networks are trained in a self-supervised manner to output the precoders. This is contrary to supervised approaches [23], [25] that require labeled datasets to compute the precoders, which is impractical for large settings. We evaluate performance-complexity trade-offs involved in the usage of lighter models, especially shallow and deep architectures of MLP. This is in contrast to the use of transformers in [26] which demand high computational complexity. The computation time [25] of the proposed precoding schemes for large user settings is evaluated against WMMSE [6]. As an extension to our previous work [38], we conduct an in-depth analysis of the radiation pattern and breakdown of the individual common and private rates in the RSMA system. The numerical analysis of critically loaded scenarios evaluates

the computational complexity of the proposed self-supervised precoding schemes to that of the demanding WMMSE precoding solution [18].

The contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- **Leveraging GNN architectures for RSMA precoder Optimization:** The wireless channel between the base station and users is viewed a graph which serves as the input to the neural network. This approach is in stark contrast with a vast majority of conventional iterative-based WMMSE approaches from the literature such as [6], [14], and [39]. Unlike the supervised approaches [23], [25], [26], we show the effectiveness of using self-supervised training to optimize the precoders.
- **Application of self-supervised training techniques to MLP architectures:** To the best of our knowledge, in the context of RSMA, this is the first time that MLPs have been implemented in self-supervised manner to output RSMA precoders. We implement shallow and deep architectures which serve as benchmarks in evaluating the GNN precoder policy. We show how lighter architectures, like GNN and MLP can offer similar performance to WMMSE precoder schemes. This is achieved without employing heavy models like transformer [27] or reinforcement learning policies [32], [33] that take long convergence time.
- **Design and analysis of RSMA precoding strategies in non-linear scenarios:** A dedicated section investigates the usage of neural network based precoding policies for non-linear scenarios. Again, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that RSMA precoding has been analyzed under the context of non-linear effects due to power amplifier effects. We formulate the sum-rate maximization problem similar to [34] and [40], but applied to RSMA beamforming. We also conduct an extensive analysis when there is a model mismatch in the training and testing phases with respect to linear and non-linear RSMA settings.
- **In-depth analysis of RSMA radiation patterns:** We conduct an in-depth analysis of the far-field radiation pattern in both linear and non-linear scenarios to evaluate the robustness of proposed data-driven precoder policies. The breakdown of common and private rates helps in evaluating the precoding policies against the ZF precoder.
- **Analysis of achievable sum-rate vs. computational complexity trade-offs:** The trade-off between achievable system capacity and computational complexity of the various neural network architectures is carefully analyzed against other conventional (i.e not data-driven) approaches from the state of the art. This includes computation time, number of trainable parameters, and number of operations for each of the precoding schemes.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II describes the RSMA system model. Section III explains the existing conventional precoder benchmarking schemes

that have been applied in RSMA. Section IV deals with the problem formulation of sum-rate maximization, followed by the specifications of the proposed neural network-based precoding schemes. The numerical simulation study is presented in Section V, while Section VI deals with the special case of precoding for non-linear channels. The computational complexity analysis is carried out in Section VII, and conclusions are finally drawn in Section VIII.

Notation: Lowercase and uppercase boldface letters denote vectors and matrices, respectively. The superscripts $(\cdot)^*$, $(\cdot)^T$, $(\cdot)^H$ denote complex conjugate, transpose, and Hermitian transpose, respectively. The $M \times M$ identity matrix is denoted by I_M . We use $A \odot B$ to denote the Hadamard (entry-wise) product of two equally-sized matrices A and B; $A \otimes B$ represents the Kronecker product of matrices; $\text{diag}(\mathbf{a})$ represents a diagonal matrix that contains the elements of the vector \mathbf{a} on its diagonal, $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{A})$ computes the trace, and $\text{diag}(\mathbf{A})$ is the main diagonal of a square matrix \mathbf{A} .

II. SIGNAL AND SYSTEM MODEL

Let us consider the downlink of a multi-user RSMA system where the Base Station (BS) is equipped with N_T transmit antennas serving K single-antenna users. We consider 1-layer RS, where the message W_k intended for the k -th user is split at the transmitter into two sub-messages, namely sub-message $W_{c,k}$ and private sub-message $W_{p,k}$. The sub-messages $W_{c,1}, \dots, W_{c,K}$ of all the users are combined into one message W_c and encoded into a common stream s_c using a codebook shared by all users. Although the entire common message W_c has to be decoded by all users, only the corresponding sub-message $W_{c,k}$ is of interest to the k -th user. The private sub-messages of all users $W_{p,1}, \dots, W_{p,K}$ are independently encoded into private streams $s_p[1], \dots, s_p[K]$, which are decoded by the respective users (illustrated in Figure 1). Therefore, $K + 1$ streams, i.e., $\mathbf{s} = [s_c, s_1, \dots, s_K]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{(K+1) \times 1}$ are created from the K messages W_1, \dots, W_K .

FIGURE 1. One-layer RS model with K users based on [6]. The common stream s_c is intended for all users, whereas private streams s_k are individual to each user.

The streams are then linearly transformed via multiplication with the precoding matrix $\mathbf{P} = [\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_K]$ where $\mathbf{p}_c, \mathbf{p}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}, k = 1, \dots, K$ are the unit-norm beamforming vectors. The transmit signal thus reads

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} = \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{A} is a diagonal matrix containing the values $\alpha_c, \alpha_k \in [0, 1]$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$, namely, the power allocation coefficients of common and private message streams, such that $\alpha_c^2 + \sum_{k=1}^K \alpha_k^2 = 1$. The received signal at the k -th user is thus given by

$$\begin{aligned} y_k &= \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n}_k \\ &= \mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{h}_k^H \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{n}_k \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}$ is the channel vector of the k -th user; \mathbf{n}_k denotes i.i.d. Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN) with zero mean and variance $\sigma_{n,k}^2$.

At the receiver, each user first decodes the common stream s_c into W_c by treating the interference from all private streams as noise. Using Successive Interference Cancellation (SIC), W_c is then re-encoded, precoded, and subtracted from the received signal. Therefore, user- k decodes its private stream s_k into $W_{p,k}$ by treating the remaining interference from the other private streams as noise. Finally, the k -th user reconstructs the original message by extracting $W_{c,k}$ from W_c , and combining $W_{c,k}$ with $W_{p,k}$ into W_k .¹ The signal-to-interference-plus-noise ratio (SINR) at k -th user for decoding the common and private streams are respectively given by

$$\gamma_{c,k} = \frac{|\alpha_c \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{p}_c|^2}{\sum_{q=1}^K |\alpha_q \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma_{p,k} = \frac{|\alpha_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{p}_k|^2}{\sum_{q=1, q \neq k}^K |\alpha_q \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2}. \quad (4)$$

The achievable rate of the common stream of k -th user is $R_{c,k} = \log(1 + \gamma_{c,k})$, while that of the private stream is $R_{p,k} = \log(1 + \gamma_{p,k})$. As the common stream must be decoded by all the users in the system, it must be transmitted at a rate not exceeding a global common minimum, namely, $R_c = \min\{R_{c,1} \dots R_{c,K}\}$. Thus, the achievable sum-rate R_{sum} for a precoding matrix $\mathbf{W} = \mathbf{P}\mathbf{A}$ reads

$$R_{\text{sum}}(\mathbf{W}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{p,k} \quad (5)$$

The precoders need to be optimized to maximize the sum-rate R_{sum} of the system as defined in (5) subject to a set of

¹For more details, the interested reader can refer to [4].

constraints:

$$\underset{\mathbf{W}}{\text{maximize}} \quad R_{\text{sum}}(\mathbf{W}) = R_c + \sum_{k=1}^K R_{p,k} \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{subject to } R_c \leq R_{c,k}, \forall k \in K \quad (6b)$$

$$\text{Tr}(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{W}^H) \leq P_t \quad (6c)$$

where (6b) ensures common stream can be decoded by all the users; and (6c) is the transmit power constraint, with P_t being the total transmit power. It should be noted that in this work, we only consider the objective of sum-rate maximization for precoder computation. We do not explicitly consider the optimization of the message split of individual user messages, because R_c being the global common minimum does not affect the overall sum-rate.

III. CONVENTIONAL PRECODER SOLUTIONS

In this section, we briefly describe a number of conventional precoding strategies which have been proposed in RSMA settings. These schemes will be used in Section V serving as benchmarks to evaluate the proposed neural network based precoding solutions.

A. ZERO FORCING-BASED PRECODERS

In Zero Forcing (ZF), the precoding vectors are structured so as to nullify the interference among users. This is the simplest, yet sub-optimal solution, and can be implemented with low computation complexity, as studied in [20], [41], [42], and [43].

In an underloaded scenario (where $N_T > K$), the first column of the precoding matrix \mathbf{P} corresponds to the precoder of the *common* stream \mathbf{p}_c , which must be built so that the message can be received by all the users in the system. To achieve this, \mathbf{p}_c is selected as the principal eigenvector (i.e., eigenvector associated to the largest eigenvalue) of the matrix $\sum_{k=1}^K \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{h}_k^H$. This is to ensure that the transmitted power is maximized towards all the directions where users are present, without any per-user priorities. With respect to the precoder vectors associated to the *private* streams, we build them to be completely orthogonal to each other to eliminate inter-user interference using zero-forcing. The precoders prior to normalization is as below.

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{ZF}} = \mathbf{H}^H (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H)^{-1} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_K]^H$ is the overall channel matrix.

As an additional benchmark, we also compute the private precoders based on Regularized Zero-forcing (RZF) which is a scaled version of ZF.

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}_{\text{RZF}} = \mathbf{H}^H (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H + \delta \mathbf{I})^{-1} \quad (8)$$

with δ being the regularization parameter. The precoding vectors are normalized and weighted according to the power allocation coefficients.

B. WMMSE-BASED PRECODERS

The optimization problem of obtaining the precoders is to maximize the sum rate defined by (5) subject to a power constraint $\text{tr}[\mathbf{W}\mathbf{W}^H] \leq P_t$, where we have assumed that the symbols $s_p[k], s_c$ are unit power and $P_t > 0$ is the total transmit power. This problem is highly non-convex, but it can be converted into an equivalent problem that is easier to handle. The main idea was introduced in [44] and [45] and later introduced in the RSMA context in [13], and consists of converting the problem of rate maximization into a problem of minimizing a weighted MMSE.

With some abuse of notation, let us denote \mathbf{w}_k and \mathbf{w}_c the columns of the precoding matrix \mathbf{W} associated to the k -th private and common streams respectively. We consider a linear estimation of the two streams at user k , namely $\hat{s}_c[k] = g_{c,k} y[k]$ (common stream) and $\hat{s}_p[k] = g_{p,k} (y[k] - \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{w}_c s_c)$ (private stream). One can easily compute its MSE with respect to the true symbols $s_p[k], s_c$ (assumed to be unit power and i.i.d.), namely

$$\text{MSE}_{c,k}(g_{c,k}, \mathbf{W}) = |g_{c,k}|^2 T_c[k] - 2\text{Re} \left[g_{c,k}^* \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{w}_c \right] + 1$$

$$\text{MSE}_{p,k}(g_{p,k}, \mathbf{W}) = |g_{p,k}|^2 T_p[k] - 2\text{Re} \left[g_{p,k}^* \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{w}_k \right] + 1$$

where

$$T_q[k] = |\mathbf{w}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2 + \sum_{q=1}^K |\mathbf{w}_q^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2 + \sigma_{n,k}^2$$

is the total received power and $T_p[k] = T_c[k] - |\mathbf{w}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2$ is the received power after subtracting the common stream. By simply forcing derivatives to zero in the above equations, one can see that the receiver weights that minimize the MSE are given by $g_{c,k}^{\text{MMSE}} = \mathbf{w}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k / T_c[k]$ and $g_{p,k}^{\text{MMSE}} = \mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{h}_k / T_p[k]$. The MMSE achieved by these two receive coefficients can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_c^{\text{MMSE}}[k] &= \text{MSE}_{c,k}(g_{c,k}^{\text{MMSE}}, \mathbf{W}) \\ &= 1 - |\mathbf{w}_c^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2 / T_c[k] = (1 + \gamma_{c,k})^{-1} \\ \varepsilon_p^{\text{MMSE}}[k] &= \text{MSE}_{p,k}(g_{p,k}^{\text{MMSE}}, \mathbf{W}) \\ &= 1 - |\mathbf{w}_k^H \mathbf{h}_k|^2 / T_p[k] = (1 + \gamma_{p,k})^{-1}. \end{aligned}$$

This establishes a direct relationship between the rates and the MMSE, showing that $R_{c,k} = -\log_2(\varepsilon_c^{\text{MMSE}}[k])$ and $R_k = -\log_2(\varepsilon_k^{\text{MMSE}}[k])$. Now, the final step consists in noticing that the minimum of the function $u \mapsto ux + \log u + 1$ (with $x > 0$ and x mapped to respective $\varepsilon^{\text{MMSE}}$) is achieved precisely at the point $u = x^{-1}$, where it takes the value $\log u$. This directly shows that we can express

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - R_{c,k} &= \min_u \left\{ u \varepsilon_c^{\text{MMSE}}[k] + \log u \right\} \\ 1 - R_{p,k} &= \min_u \left\{ u \varepsilon_p^{\text{MMSE}}[k] + \log u \right\} \end{aligned}$$

implying that

$$1 - R_{c,k} = \min_{u_k, g_{c,k}} \{u \text{MSE}_{c,k}(g_{c,k}, \mathbf{W}) + \log u\}$$

$$1 - R_{p,k} = \min_{u_k, g_{p,k}} \{u \text{MSE}_{p,k}(g_{p,k}, \mathbf{W}) + \log u\}.$$

By collecting the variables u_k , $g_{c,k}$ and $g_{p,k}$ for $k = 1, \dots, K$ into K -dimensional vectors \mathbf{u} , \mathbf{g}_c , \mathbf{g}_p and letting $\mathbf{G} = [\mathbf{g}_c, \mathbf{g}_p]$, the original problem can therefore be equivalently formulated as

$$\min_{\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{G}, \mathbf{W}, E_c} E_c + \sum_{k=1}^K (u \text{MSE}_{p,k}(g_{p,k}, \mathbf{W}) + \log u)$$

subject to the constraints $\text{tr}(\mathbf{W}\mathbf{W}^H) \leq P_t$

$$u \text{MSE}_{c,k}(g_{c,k}, \mathbf{W}) + \log u \leq E_c \quad (k = 1, \dots, K).$$

where E_c is the common MSE. It should be noted that the optimization problem in each separate variable is convex.

The WMMSE algorithm sequentially solves the problem for each of these three variables sequentially. The optimization with respect \mathbf{G} and \mathbf{u} decouples in the different users, and the corresponding solution accepts a closed form. The only step that requires some additional computation is the optimization with respect to the precoding vectors \mathbf{W} , the closed form solution cannot be derived [6]. It can be formulated as a quadratically constrained quadratic problem solvable by conventional methods (note that $\text{MSE}_{c,k}$ and $\text{MSE}_{p,k}$ are quadratic functions of the precoder vector). The algorithm in [6] is depicted below. It can be shown to converge, although in general there is no guarantee of convergence to the global optimum (only to a local extreme).

Algorithm 1 Alternating Optimization Algorithm Based on [6], [44], and [45]

- 1: **Initialize:** $n \leftarrow 0$, $\mathbf{W}^{[n]}$, $\text{WSR}^{[n]}$
- 2: **repeat**
- 3: $n \leftarrow n + 1$
- 4: $\mathbf{W}^{[n-1]} \leftarrow \mathbf{W}$
- 5: $\mathbf{u} \leftarrow \mathbf{u}^{\text{MMSE}}(\mathbf{W}^{n-1})$
- 6: $\mathbf{g} \leftarrow \mathbf{g}^{\text{MMSE}}(\mathbf{W}^{n-1})$
- 7: update \mathbf{W} using the updated \mathbf{u} and \mathbf{g} with CVX tool
- 8: **until** $|\text{WSR}^{[n]} - \text{WSR}^{[n-1]}| \leq \epsilon$
- 9: n

IV. NEURAL NETWORKS FOR PRECODING

In this section, we formulate the problem of precoder optimization in such a way that it can be solved using neural networks (NN). We look into the use of Graph Neural Network (GNN), shallow (one layer) and deep architectures of Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) based solutions.

A. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The neural networks considered in this work take as input the overall (linear) channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N_T}$ and outputs the

precoding matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{W}} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times (K+1)}$. Thus, we have

$$\widehat{\mathbf{W}} = f(\mathbf{H}; \theta)$$

where θ denotes the trainable parameters of the NN. In other words, the training of the NN is performed in a self-supervised manner by minimizing the negative of the sum rate, that is

$$\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} -R_{\text{sum}}(f(\mathbf{H}; \theta)). \quad (9)$$

Since the SINR of the common and private streams depend on the precoders, the neural networks are trained to achieve precoder optimization using gradient descent and backpropagation.

B. GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK

The RSMA precoding problem can be regarded as learning a (non-linear) mapping from a $K \times N_T$ channel matrix to a $N_T \times (K+1)$ precoding matrix. The N_T transmit antennas and K users can be viewed as nodes of a graph, while each of the $N_E = K \cdot N_T$ edges of the graph holds a number of features or embeddings. Specifically, the L -layer GNN consists of: (i) one input layer depicting the wireless network as a graph with each of the edges containing the real and imaginary parts of corresponding channel coefficient; (ii) $L - 2$ hidden layers that implement the Message Passing Algorithm (MPA) with $d_l(l = 2, \dots, L - 2)$ edge features each²; (iii) one output layer providing the estimated precoder coefficients (see details ahead in this section).

Message Passing Algorithm (MPA): The embedding of each edge (t, r) in layer l is represented as $z_{(t,r)}^l$. At the input layer $l = 1$, it holds the real and imaginary coefficients of the channel along the particular edge i.e., $z_{(t,r)}^1 = [\text{Re}(h_{t,r}), \text{Im}(h_{t,r})]^T$. In each of the hidden layers, the operations consist of message-passing iterations and an update step, which is expressed as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$ and $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ are the messages aggregated from the neighboring nodes of edge (t, r) , which is defined as

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(t,x)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(t) \} \right) \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)} = \text{AGGREGATE}^{(l)} \left(\{ \mathbf{z}_{(x,r)}^{(l)}, \forall x \in \mathcal{N}(r) \} \right) \quad (12)$$

The mechanism of the message passing algorithm (MPA) in the l -th hidden layer is shown in Figure 2. It should be noted that the UPDATE and AGGREGATE must be differentiable functions [36] that need to be defined.

The update rule in (10) can be expanded as below

$$\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)} = \text{UPDATE}^{(l)} \left(\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)}, \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right)$$

$$= \sigma \left(\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} + \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)} \mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} \right) \quad (13)$$

²In the jargon of GNNs, each *hidden* layer refers to one iteration of the MPA.

FIGURE 2. GNN for RSMA precoder computation, visualized for a single edge (0,0) in the graph. The message passing operations are shown in (a) message aggregation at the receive nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}$ and (b) message aggregation at the transmit nodes $\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}$; and (c) updated edge features as per the update rule (10).

where $\mathbf{z}_{(t,r)}^{(l+1)}$ denotes the hidden representation of the edge (t, r) at the $(l + 1)$ layer of the GNN, $\sigma(\cdot)$ is a non-linear activation function and the matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)} \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{l+1} \times d_l}$ are the learnable weights of GNN to be optimized using stochastic gradient descent. In this work, Rectified Linear Units (ReLU) are used as activation functions in all hidden layers [46].

Similar to [35] and [47], we define the message aggregation (via the AGGREGATE function in (11) and (12)) passed between the nodes as follows

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(t)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(t)|} \sum_{r' \in \mathcal{N}(t)} \mathbf{z}_{(t,r')}^{(l)} \quad (14)$$

$$\mathbf{m}_{\mathcal{N}(r)}^{(l)} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{N}(r)|} \sum_{t' \in \mathcal{N}(r)} \mathbf{z}_{(t',r)}^{(l)}. \quad (15)$$

The above choice keeps the computational complexity low and shows the effectiveness of simple aggregation methods over other weighted variants [36]. The dimensions d_{l+1} and d_l of the weight matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)}$ determine the number of features in layers $(l + 1)$ and l , respectively. For the RSMA precoding problem, the input layer of GNN has $d_0 = 2$ features (real and imaginary parts of the channel coefficient). The optimum number of edge features d_l of the hidden layers is found via hyperparameter tuning. The readout module involves flattening of the edge features, followed by reshape through a linear layer to output the required number of output features, that is, the real and imaginary parts of the precoder matrix. To fulfill the power constraint, a power normalization layer is applied to the output, which consists of a scalar normalization given by

$$\widehat{\mathbf{W}}^{\text{norm}} = \zeta \widehat{\mathbf{W}} \quad (16)$$

with $\zeta = \sqrt{P_T / \text{Tr}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}\widehat{\mathbf{W}}^H)}$.

Based on the above architecture, the GNN is able to learn a non-linear mapping parameterized by θ which includes all the trainable matrices $\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_t^{(l)}, \mathbf{W}_r^{(l)}$. The training is done in a self-supervised manner by maximizing the negative sum rate in order to optimize the neural network parameters. The gradients of the sum rate loss function is dependent on SINR,

which in turn is dependent on the precoder matrix $\widehat{\mathbf{W}}$ that is output from the neural network. Thus the gradients with respect to the neural network parameters θ , can be directly computed using back-propagation. Given these gradients, the parameters of the GNN are updated using the Adam optimizer.

FIGURE 3. The complete architecture of GNN model for RSMA precoder computation.

In this work, we employ one hidden layer (iteration) for the GNN because of the simple nature of the input graph where all the transmit and user antennas are connected via edges. The complete architecture is depicted in Figure 3. The input graph is a many-to-many connections from transmit antennas to the users in the system, defined on a bipartite graph. Edge-GNN is the GNN model that performs message passing algorithm as shown in Equation (13). The message aggregated over one-hop neighborhood is able to gather relevant statistics for computing the precoder matrix, thus not requiring multiple layers which would be needed to aggregate information of nodes/edges over multiple hops [36]. We validated this by running simulations with 2 and 3 hidden layers, but they resulted in marginal gains in terms of achievable sum rate. The one-layer message hopping holds valid for environments with a single base-station serving any number of users (underloaded, critically loaded, and overloaded scenarios). The number of edges scales with the number of transmit antennas and users in the system, hence not requiring hyperparameter optimization like in MLPs.

C. MULTI-LAYER PERCEPTRON

The self-supervised precoder design problem can also be solved via feed-forward Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). Specifically, it can be cast into a regression task where:

- The input of the DNN is the overall channel matrix \mathbf{H} re-shaped into a row vector $\mathbf{i} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\mathbf{H}) \otimes [0, 1]]$.
- The output is the computed precoders $\mathbf{o} = \text{vec}[\text{Re}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}) \otimes [1, 0] + \text{Im}(\widehat{\mathbf{W}}) \otimes [0, 1]]$

Feed-forward Deep Neural Networks includes the Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). The L -layer MLP (see Figure 4) consists of: (i) one input layer with $2KN_T$ elements (the real and imaginary parts of the channel matrix); (ii) one output layer with $2N_T(K + 1)$ neurons; and (iii) $L - 2$ hidden layers with $N_l; l = 2, \dots, L - 1$ neurons each. This MLP defines a mapping $f(t, \Phi) : \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_P} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{2N_R N_T}$ of an input vector t

FIGURE 4. MLP for precoding.

onto an output vector \mathbf{r}_L through L processing steps:

$$r_l = f_l(r_{l-1}; \phi_l); \quad l = 1 \dots L \quad (17)$$

where $f_l(r_{l-1}, \phi_l) : \mathbb{R}^{N_{l-1}} \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{N_l}$ is the mapping associated to the l -th layer. Such mapping depends on the output from the previous layer and also the parameter set of the concerned layer, ϕ_l , with $\Phi = [\phi_1, \dots, \phi_L]$ denoting the set of all parameters in the model. A power normalization layer is applied to the final output, which consists of a scalar normalization given by Equation (16).

Similar to the previous architecture, ReLU is used as activation functions in all hidden layers. We do not use normalization and dropout layers as this was found to be counterproductive in most regression problems [48].

V. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

In this section, we first assess the performance of the proposed GNN and MLP schemes in terms of Achievable Sum-Rate (ASR), followed by the impact of channel estimation error, and radiation pattern analysis. The scenarios considered are with $K = \{2, 8, 32, 64\}$ single-antenna users, and $N_T = \{3, 9, 32, 64\}$ transmit antennas, respectively. The various scenarios are categorized based on the number of streams in the system with respect to the number of transmit antennas N_T . For first two cases, there are as many streams ($K + 1$) as (N_T), we term this as critically-loaded scenarios. The last two cases are overloaded systems with $N_T < (K + 1)$. The user channels are modeled as Gaussian random vector with entries being circularly symmetric and drawn independently for each realization [49]. The the channel vector of the k -th user $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times 1}$ is drawn independently from $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. As for the power allocation coefficients $\{\alpha_c, \alpha_k\}$ of ZF and the initialization of WMMSE benchmarks, 90% of P_t is allocated to the common precoder, 10% is equally distributed among the K private precoders (similar to [13], [25]). This ensures low error propagation from common stream detection to private stream detection

due to improper SIC. In the case of neural networks, they are estimated as part of the precoder output.

We train the neural networks in the described *self-supervised* manner to compute the precoders at SNR of 20dB for each channel realization. We use this set of precoders to compute sum-rate across SNR range of -10dB to 30dB. For the implementation, training, and evaluation of the proposed schemes, we use PyTorch. For the Adam optimizer, the learning rate is set to 0.01. The neural networks based on GNN and MLP architectures are trained for 50 epochs, to ensure they reach convergence. We performed grid-search hyperparameter optimization in order to determine the N_l neurons of the *shallow* MLPs in the search space of $\{64 - 1024\}$ neurons. The optimal neurons for $K = [2, 8, 32, 64]$ users was found out to be $N_l = [128, 256, 512, 1024]$ neurons, respectively. For *deep* MLPs, we simply added two more hidden layers in order to boost the learning capacity. With respect to GNNs, the optimum number of edge features d_l in the hidden layers turned out to be 4 features, after performing hyperparameter tuning in the range of $[2, 4, 8]$. A summary of the above parameters is included in Table 1.

A. ACHIEVABLE SUM RATE (LINEAR)

The neural networks take as input the overall channel matrix \mathbf{H} to compute the precoders. In this specific subsection, we assume perfect instantaneous CSIT across all precoding schemes. As benchmarks, we have followed the implementation of WMMSE for RSMA [6] and the sub-optimal solution based on zero-forcing (ZF) and Regularized Zero-forcing (RZF) with $\delta = \frac{1}{\text{SNR}}$.

Figure 5 depicts the achievable sum-rate as a function of the SNR for the scenarios considered averaged for 100 channel realizations. For the case of $K = 2$ users, the gap between ZF and WMMSE performance is marginal, with the neural networks exhibiting similar performance to ZF. In the case of $K = 8$ users, neural network-based precoders offer substantial gain in the mid-SNR region, when compared to ZF.

In the more realistic overloaded scenarios of 32 and 64 users as shown in Figure 6, ZF and RZF do not offer satisfactory performance, whereas the performance of neural network-based schemes is virtually identical to that of the WMMSE algorithm for all SNRs. This is achieved at a much reduced computational time as it will be discussed in Section VII ahead. When compared to ZF, the neural network based schemes offer almost four orders of improvement at 20dB. In addition to the average sum-rate achieved, the standard deviation bars are also depicted at each SNR. In critically-loaded scenarios (Figure 5), all the precoding schemes show reliability in terms of low standard deviation. However, in over-loaded scenarios (Figure 6), the zero-forcing solution shows a significantly higher standard deviation at 30dB. The self-supervised schemes follow the pattern exhibited by WMMSE and record minimal standard deviation across the SNR range.

TABLE 1. Hyperparameters for different neural network schemes.

	Multi-layer Perceptron	Graph Neural Network
Number of hidden layers	1 (Shallow) 3 (Deep)	2
Number of epochs	50	50
Customized Loss function	Equation (6a)	Equation (6a)
Number of neurons (MLP) Number of edge features (GNN) (for different K users)		
2	128	4
4	256	4
32	512	4
64	1024	4

FIGURE 5. Achievable Sum-Rate of the precoder optimization solutions in critically-loaded scenarios.

B. IMPACT OF CHANNEL ESTIMATION ERROR (LINEAR, IMPERFECT CSIT)

The quality of the channel state information at the transmitter (CSIT) may have a substantial impact on the achievable sum rate of the precoding policies. In this subsection, we consider the impact of CSIT error on the computation of precoders. The noisy channel estimate $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ (instead of \mathbf{H}) is modeled as $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{H} + \mathbf{Q}$, where $\mathbf{Q} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times N_T}$ represents zero-mean AWGN of variance β^2 . With imperfect precoders, the orthogonality of the private messages is not preserved, leading to poor ASR.

In Figure 7 (x-axis in log scale), it is observed that the ASR decreases as the channel estimation error increases. The degradation rate has been analyzed at different SNR, solid

FIGURE 6. Achievable Sum-Rate of the precoder optimization solutions in over-loaded scenarios.

lines depict for 30dB, while the dashed are for 20dB. For the system with 8 users (critically-loaded scenario, top subplot), ZF benchmark degrades faster than MLP and GNN schemes for $\beta^2 > 10^{-2}$. For 64 users (overloaded scenario, bottom subplot), the NN schemes follow the descending pattern exhibited by the WMMSE benchmark. Shallow MLP records slightly lower performance than deep MLP, whereas GNN offers similar performance to deep MLP using reduced number of trainable parameters (Section VII-A).

C. RADIATION PATTERNS

The radiation patterns of the precoding schemes are studied to evaluate the different streams in the RSMA system. Unlike other sections, here we resort to pure line-of-sight (LoS)

FIGURE 7. Achievable sum rate for various precoding policies under different noise variance of CSIT. The solid lines correspond to SNR 30dB, while the dashed are for 20dB.

channels to analyze the directivity of the different precoders. The transmit antennas in the system model are assumed to be arranged as a uniform linear array (ULA) with $\lambda_c/2$ spacing, where λ_c is the carrier wavelength). We consider a single-path LoS channel between the transmitter and the k -th user with an angle of departure (AoD) of ψ_k . The channel coefficients for the plane-wave model for $t = 1, \dots, N_T$ is expressed as

$$[\mathbf{h}(\psi_k)]_t = e^{-j\pi(t-1)\cos(\psi_k)} \quad (18)$$

In studying the radiation pattern of RSMA scenario, we expect to see two main lobes for each user - one for the common stream and one for the intended private stream. We first analyze for the simplest case of 2 users served by a BS with $N_T = 3$ antennas. In Figure 8, the radiation pattern for the different precoding schemes considered in this paper are shown alongside the benchmarks. The AWGN noise floor at 20dB has been depicted for reference purposes. The location of each of the users is depicted using dotted red lines. As expected, each user experiences two main lobes pertaining to common stream and intended private stream, while a null is placed at the interfering private stream of the other user. The nulls defined on the interfering stream are the deepest in ZF precoder, but these nulls are well below the noise floor. For an extensive analysis, the radiation pattern must be

FIGURE 8. Radiation pattern for the different precoding schemes ($N_T = 3$, $K = 2$, $\psi = [150^\circ, 90^\circ]$).

evaluated alongside the numerically recorded common and private rates.

Table 2 records the breakdown of achievable rates by the different precoding schemes for the LoS scenario. It shows that the highest common rate achieved is from the use of MLP precoding scheme, which corresponds to the higher power level of the common stream radiation pattern of MLP in Figure 8. The ZF and WMMSE record lower common rates, whereas the private rates are substantially higher than those of MLP. On the other hand, the GNN precoding scheme shows a balance between the two extremes. It achieves a common rate higher than WMMSE, and private rates that are higher than MLP. This is attributed to the inherent structure of the GNN architecture, which models the wireless channel as a graph, capturing complex spatial relationships between users and transmit antennas. By representing network interactions as graph edges and nodes, GNNs naturally encode dependencies between different elements in the system. The maximum private rate achieved by GNN is closer to that of the WMMSE benchmark. This analysis shows that although all the precoding schemes exhibit similar achievable sum rates (as shown in Figure 5), each of them learn completely different policies. Some schemes favor higher common rate allocation, while others achieve higher private rates for the users in the system.

We extend the analysis to critically-loaded case, for 8 users being served by $N_T = 9$ antennas, accounting for a total of 9 streams in the system. For visualization purposes, we have only shown 2 of the private streams for each of the precoding schemes in Figure 9 along with the common stream. Yet again, the nulls defined by the ZF precoding scheme are the deepest among all the schemes. In the WMMSE precoding scheme, the common stream is far below the error floor. This implies that in overloaded scenarios, the highest achievable sum rate is brought about by switching off the common stream and dedicating the power allocation to private streams.

TABLE 2. Breakdown of achievable rates by different precoding schemes at 30dB ($N_T = 3, K = 2, \psi = [150^\circ, 90^\circ]$).

	Common Rate [bps/Hz]	Private Rates [bps/Hz]		
	MIN	MIN	MAX	MEAN
ZF	0.50	5.52	5.52	5.52
WMMSE	0.41	6.82	6.82	6.82
MLP	7.56	2.25×10^{-4}	1.39×10^{-4}	1.82×10^{-4}
GNN	1.42	3.94	6.65	5.29

TABLE 3. Breakdown of achievable rates by different precoding schemes ($N_T = 9, K = 8, \psi = [150^\circ, 130^\circ, 120^\circ, 100^\circ, 90^\circ, 60^\circ, 20^\circ, 10^\circ]$).

	Common Rate [bps/Hz]	Private Rates [bps/Hz]		
	MIN	MIN	MAX	MEAN
ZF	0.08	2.91	2.92	2.91
WMMSE	1.32×10^{-13}	1.29×10^{-12}	6.77	5.88
MLP	2.51	8.58×10^{-5}	4.68	4.01
GNN	1.18	6.81×10^{-4}	6.90	5.76

FIGURE 9. Radiation pattern for the different precoding schemes ($N_T = 9, K = 8, \psi = [150^\circ, 130^\circ, 120^\circ, 100^\circ, 90^\circ, 60^\circ, 20^\circ, 10^\circ]$).

Unlike WMMSE, the MLP and GNN precoding schemes still exploit common streams. In Table 3, the MLP scheme records the highest common rate, while GNN manages the second highest of all the precoding schemes.

In the analysis of private rates, GNN records a higher mean rate than MLP. This is very close to the mean private rate achieved by the WMMSE precoding scheme. We also notice that at least one of the private streams is turned off in all of the iterative precoding schemes. This is a consequence of the water-filling effect [49] where the users with high channel interference are allocated the least power, or in some cases turned off. Nonetheless, even in critically loaded scenario, GNN offers a good trade-off between MLP and WMMSE precoding schemes. It achieves private rates higher than MLP and a moderately high common rate. This is in stark contrast to WMMSE which turns off the common stream.

VI. SPECIAL CASE: PRECODING FOR NON-LINEAR CHANNELS

Here, we investigate the impact of non-linearities in the end-to-end communications channel on precoding policies. Specifically, we focus on non-linear effects introduced by the

power amplifier (PA) used at the transmitter. To incorporate such effects, however, first we need to enhance the signal model that was presented in Section II.

A. SIGNAL MODEL

The input of the PA is a bandpass signal which can be modeled as:

$$x(t) = A(t)e^{j\varphi(t)} \tag{19}$$

The output of the non-linear PA is as given below

$$y(t) = \phi(x(t)) \tag{20}$$

$$= \phi_A(A(t))e^{j\varphi(t)+\phi_\varphi(A(t))} \tag{21}$$

where $\phi_A(\cdot)$ and $\phi_\varphi(\cdot)$ represent the amplitude modulation to amplitude modulation (AM/AM) and amplitude to phase modulation (AM/PM) transfer functions, respectively.

Similar to [34] and [40], the impact of nonlinear distortion on the system performance is modeled using Bussgang's theorem [50], which defines the nonlinearly distorted signal $\phi(\mathbf{x})$ as below

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{B}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{e} \tag{22}$$

where $\mathbf{B} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_T \times N_T}$ is a diagonal gain matrix, and $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ is the distortion term, which is uncorrelated with \mathbf{x} (under gaussian signaling). We make use of a third-order polynomial to model the nonlinear PAs at the transmitter as follows

$$\phi(x) = \beta_1 x + \beta_3 x|x|^2 \tag{23}$$

where $\beta_1 \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\beta_3 \in \mathbb{C}$ are the model parameters, assumed to be known at the transmitter. The input back-off (IBO) is defined as $IBO = p_{in}/p_{sat}$ where p_{in} is the average input power and p_{sat} is the saturation power of each PA. The polynomial coefficients at desired IBO can be obtained by using least squares regression of the polynomial model to the modified Rapp model [35]. The corresponding AM/AM and AM/PM distortion of the modified Rapp model are

$$\phi_A(x) = \frac{|x|}{\left(1 + \left|\frac{x}{\sqrt{p_{sat}}}\right|^{2S}\right)^{\frac{1}{2S}}} \tag{24}$$

$$\phi_\varphi(x) = \frac{A|x|^q}{1 + \left|\frac{x}{B}\right|^q} \tag{25}$$

The modified Rapp model coefficients are set to $S = 2$, $q = 4$, $A = -0.315$, $B = 1.137$, closely following [35]. The gain matrix \mathbf{B} depends on the precoding matrix \mathbf{P} as

$$\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) = \beta_1 \mathbf{I}_M + 2\beta_3 \text{diag}(\mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}^H) \quad (26)$$

From all the above, the updated received signal of the k -th user reads as

$$\mathbf{y}_k = \alpha_c \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \mathbf{p}_c s_c + \alpha_k \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \mathbf{p}_k s_k + \sum_{j \neq k} \alpha_j \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{e} + \mathbf{n}_k \quad (27)$$

It should be noted that the effective noise term

$$\sum_{j \neq k} \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \alpha_j \mathbf{p}_j s_j + \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{e} + \mathbf{n}_k$$

is non-Gaussian distributed due to the non-linearity at the transmitter. The signal-to-interference-noise and distortion ratio (SINDR) at k -th user for decoding the common and private streams are given by the respective equations below.

$$\gamma_{c,k}^{\text{SINDR}} = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \alpha_c \mathbf{p}_c|^2}{\sum_{q=1}^K |\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \alpha_q \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{C}_e(\mathbf{P}) \mathbf{h}_k^* + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (28)$$

$$\gamma_{p,k}^{\text{SINDR}} = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \alpha_k \mathbf{p}_k|^2}{\sum_{q \neq k} |\mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{P}) \alpha_q \mathbf{p}_q|^2 + \mathbf{h}_k^H \mathbf{C}_e(\mathbf{P}) \mathbf{h}_k^* + \sigma_{n,k}^2} \quad (29)$$

where $\mathbf{C}_e(\mathbf{P}) \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is the covariance of the distortion \mathbf{e} [40], which can be computed as follows:

$$\mathbf{C}_e(\mathbf{P}) = 2|\beta_3|^2 (\mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}^H \odot \mathbf{P}^* \mathbf{P}^T \odot \mathbf{P}\mathbf{P}^H) \quad (30)$$

In conclusion, in non-linear settings the sum-rate maximization problem in Equations (6a) to (6c) is governed by the SINDR expressions above instead of SINRs.

B. ANALYSIS OF THE ACHIEVABLE SUM-RATE

The achievable sum-rates for underloaded and critically-loaded scenarios are shown in Figure 10. A number of combinations of linear and non-linear channels for both the training and test phases are considered, namely

- Precoding schemes trained and tested with linear channels (dashed lines).
- Precoding schemes trained with linear channels and tested with non-linear channels (dotted lines).
- Non-linear channels for both training and test phases (solid lines).

The non-linear model parameters of (23) are set to $\beta_1 = 1$ and $\beta_3 = -0.883 - 0.058j$ for IBO = -1.5dB.

First, we observe the effect of model mismatch by comparing the dashed lines with dotted lines. When the precoding schemes are trained for linear channels and tested on non-linear channels, all the schemes perform poorly. In the low-SNR regime, the WMMSE benchmark achieves

FIGURE 10. Achievable Sum-Rate of the precoder optimization solutions for non-linear channels in the training and testing phases (solid lines), linear channels in both phases (dashed lines), and linear for training and non-linear channels for testing phases (dotted lines). Results are given for underloaded (top) and critically-loaded (bottom) scenarios.

higher sum rate, but starts to saturate beyond 20 dB in both the underloaded and critically-loaded scenarios. Further analysis revealed that, for high SNRs, the magnitude of the contribution from the term $\mathbf{C}_e(\mathbf{P})$ in the denominator of the SINDR expressions (28)-(29) was the highest in WMMSE, whereas the rest of the precoding schemes showed lower values. This, of course, results into lower achievable rates in this regime for WMMSE. It is also worth noting that self-supervised neural networks precoding schemes (GNN and MLP curves) achieve higher system capacity than ZF precoding. The drop in performance of all the schemes is significantly higher in the critically-loaded regime.

The next comparison is between the solid lines and dotted lines, revealing the tradeoff obtained from including the non-linear modeling in SINDR formulation. In both underloaded and critically loaded scenarios, the neural networks achieve significantly higher sum rates with the incorporation of the non-linear model in the training procedure, especially in the high-SNR regime. Interestingly, the MLP and GNN precoding schemes exhibit similar performance for the critically-loaded scenario of 8 users served by $N_T = 9$ antennas (bottom sub-plot) with GNN slightly outperforming MLP at high-SNR. The neural networks do not show the saturation

behavior as observed by the dotted WMMSE benchmark. The self-supervised training of the neural networks enables them to learn to maximize the achievable sum-rate, by accounting for the non-linear distortion in the RSMA system. The implementation of distortion-aware WMMSE is beyond the scope of this work, thus we do not show the relevant benchmark. However, the research findings in [35] point out that neural network-based precoding schemes outperform distortion-aware beamforming in MIMO scenarios. We theorize that similar results could be expected in RSMA systems as well. For a complete analysis, we must analyze the radiation pattern of the precoding schemes in non-linear scenarios, which is conducted in the next subsection.

FIGURE 11. Radiation pattern for the different precoding schemes in the non-linear case: ZF (top), MLP (middle), and GNN (bottom). The blue lines denote the directions where users are located ($N_T = 9, K = 2, \psi = [150^\circ, 90^\circ]$).

C. ANALYSIS OF RADIATION PATTERNS

We must analyze the radiated linear power and the distortion power. For a given precoding matrix, they are defined as follows:

$$\rho_{\text{lin}}(\psi) = \mathbf{h}^T(\psi)\mathbf{B}\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H\mathbf{B}^H\mathbf{h}^*(\psi) \quad (31)$$

$$\rho_{\text{dist}}(\psi) = \mathbf{h}^T(\psi)\mathbf{C}_e\mathbf{h}^*(\psi) \quad (32)$$

Figure 11 shows the radiation pattern for ZF, MLP, and GNN precoder schemes for the underloaded scenario of 2 users served by $N_T = 9$ antennas. In ZF precoding, the distortion beamforming lobes are directed towards the other users in the system this causing severe performance degradation. On the contrary, MLP and GNN precoding schemes show suppressed lobes in the direction of the users. In critically-loaded scenario depicted in Figure 12, the neural network schemes show distorted radiation pattern that is lower in power compared to ZF distorted signal. For visualization purposes, we only show 2 of the private streams for each of the precoding schemes along with the common stream. For the ZF precoding scheme, the distorted signal is

FIGURE 12. Radiation pattern for the different precoding schemes in the non-linear case: ZF (top), MLP (middle), and GNN (bottom). The blue lines denote the directions where users are located ($N_T = 9, K = 8, \psi = [150^\circ, 130^\circ, 120^\circ, 100^\circ, 90^\circ, 60^\circ, 20^\circ, 10^\circ]$).

much closer to the intended signal which explains the lowest sum-rate capacity achieved by ZF precoding benchmark in Figure 10 (bottom subplot).

VII. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS

In this section, we conduct an in-depth analysis of the computational complexity of the proposed precoding schemes. The analysis carried out in terms of number of trainable parameters and number of operations. We also show the computation time required by the proposed schemes in comparison to the conventional WMMSE benchmark for critically-loaded and overloaded scenarios.

A. NUMBER OF TRAINABLE PARAMETERS

The total number of trainable parameters depends on (i) the number of hidden layers in the DNN. In this work, it is set as 1 for shallow MLPs in order to analyze low computationally complex architectures. For deep MLPs, the number of hidden layers is set to 3 to analyze complex architectures; (ii) the number of hidden features (d_l) for GNNs (iii) the number of inputs $2KN_T$; (iv) the number of neurons at the output layer, which is the total number of real values to be estimated (real and imaginary precoder matrix coefficients) $N_L = 2N_T(K + 1)$; (v) the number of neurons at the hidden layers (N_l) for DNNs.

As depicted in Figure 13, GNNs record the least number of trainable parameters compared to shallow and deep MLPs for the whole range of number of transmit antennas and users. This stark difference (note y-axis is in log-scale) is because in GNNs, the same weights ($\mathbf{W}_{\text{edge}}, \mathbf{W}_t, \mathbf{W}_r$) are used for each edge to compute the precoder coefficients, unlike MLP which demands higher number of neurons as the system scales up, validating that GNNs are scalable

architectures. The plot also verifies that GNNs scale well as the system dimension increases without the need for intense hyperparameter-tuning [36].

FIGURE 13. Number of trainable parameters for each of the precoder optimization solutions.

B. COMPUTATION TIME

In order to compare the neural network schemes against the conventional iterative WMMSE algorithm, we analyze the computation time required by each of the schemes. The algorithms are implemented in Python. We do not make a comparison of the MLP versus GNN as different Python libraries are used for their respective implementation. GNN has been implemented using the PyTorch Geometric library [51], which is specifically built to easily code and train GNNs, while the MLPs are coded using PyTorch.

Figure 14 (x-axis in log scale) reveals that the neural network precoding schemes require less time in reaching convergence. As pointed out in [25] and [52], WMMSE algorithm is not computationally-friendly as the number of transmit antennas and users scale up. For both scenarios shown in the figure, WMMSE is the most time consuming algorithm. The neural networks are reaching convergence while WMMSE still completes the first iteration. The performance (achievable sum-rate) of the precoding policies were similar in both the extreme cases of zero correlation (CSCG) and complete correlation (LoS) channels. Irrespective of the type of channel model used, the computation time of the precoder optimization solutions reveals that the neural network precoding schemes require less time in reaching convergence.

C. NUMBER OF OPERATIONS

Since the neural networks are trained in a self-supervised manner, the number of operations needed include the operations performed in both the forward pass and backward propagation of gradients. The computational complexity in both the forward and backward propagation are related and dependent on the number of weights in neural network.

An overview of the complexity analysis is shown in Table 4, where M denotes the number of transmit antennas and K the number of users. Zero-forcing being the simplest solution involves a couple of matrix multiplications and matrix inverse computation. It should be noted the each

FIGURE 14. Computation time of the precoder optimization solutions.

complex multiplication requires 4 real multiplication and 2 real additions, while a complex addition requires 2 real additions. The number of operations for the MLP solution depends on the number of layers L , the number of neurons N_l , and the respective input and output layer size. As for GNN, the number of edges scale up as the number of transmit antennas and users increase; the message passing algorithm accounts for the largest number of operations. As for the WMMSE solution, apart from matrix multiplications involved for computing the equalizers and user weights [52], the complexity of the convex optimization subroutine (CVX) increases dramatically at the rate of $\mathcal{O}(M^3)$. The CVX subroutine is an iterative solver that is called D times for each epoch of the WMMSE algorithm. The MLP, GNN, and WMMSE operations are repeated for E epochs. We employ early-stopping criterion when convergence of the ASR is reached. This is defined when the difference between the mean-ASR in a sliding window of preceding 10 epochs is less than or equal to 10^{-3} bps/Hz.

In Table 4, we also include as a benchmark the deep-unfolding model RS-BNN proposed in [28]. Still, its complexity is significantly higher than that of our proposed self-supervised GNN architecture. First, the RS-BNN model involves $L_u = 5$ unfolded iterations/layers. Each of the L_u unfolded iterations consists of one input layer, one hidden layer of $N_l = 512$ hidden neurons, and one output layer to predict the Lagrangian variables. Alternatively, the

TABLE 4. Computational complexity of different precoder schemes in the prediction phase.

Variable	ZF	MLP	GNN	WMMSE [6]	Deep-unfolding [28]
Multiplications	$\mathcal{O}(K^3 + K^2M)$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKN_I + N_I^2L))$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKd_I^2L))$	$\mathcal{O}(ED(M^3 + K^2M^2))$	$\mathcal{O}(L_u(N_IKM + M^2K + K^2M))$
Additions	$\mathcal{O}(K^3 + K^2M)$	$\mathcal{O}(E(N_IL))$	$\mathcal{O}(E(MKd_I^2L + M^2Kd_IL + MK^2d_IL))$	$\mathcal{O}(ED(M^3 + K^2M^2))$	$\mathcal{O}(L_u(N_IKM + M^2K + K^2M))$

FIGURE 15. Number of multiplication and addition operations for each of the precoder optimization solutions.

FIGURE 16. Number of operations for each of the precoder optimization solutions.

gradient descent method proposed in [30] achieves the sum-rate performance of WMMSE with lesser number of iterations. However, the simulation results are only shown for under-loaded settings of 4 transmit antennas and 2 users requiring a training dataset of 1000 channel realizations. This indicates that the gradient descent method would require larger labeled precoder datasets for larger settings. We investigate in critically-loaded and over-loaded RSMA settings, where the need for efficient precoder optimization policies is critical.

Figure 15 shows the breakdown of number of multiplications and additions required by each of the NN schemes compared against ZF. Since the exact number of CVX subroutine iterations (D) cannot be computed, the WMMSE bars are omitted, nonetheless being an alternating optimization (AO) algorithm, it accounts for the highest number of operations compared to any other scheme [6]. It should also be noted that the high computation time required by WMMSE (as evaluated in Section VII-VII-B) is an indicator of the high number of operations involved.

As depicted in Figure 15, (y-axis in log scale), NN-based precoder solutions demand higher number of operations

compared to the sub-optimal ZF precoders. Shallow and Deep MLPs show increasing number of operations as the system size scales up. Interestingly, GNNs require lower number of multiplications than shallow MLPs, almost by an order. The number of additions (right sub-plot) required by GNN seems to grow at a faster rate than the number of multiplications. Thus, at 64 × 64, GNN precoding scheme requires greater number of additions, compared with deep MLP. In order to evaluate the overall computational complexity, we look at the total number of operations as plotted in Figure 16. The number of operations required by GNNs is lesser than that of the MLPs. They all show an upward trend as the number of transmit antennas and users increase.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This paper investigated the use of self-supervised learning techniques for precoder optimization in RSMA-based MIMO systems. We proposed two architectures —Graph Neural Networks (GNN) and deep or shallow Multi-Layer Perceptrons (MLP)— as alternatives to conventional iterative methods like WMMSE. Our results demonstrated that these neural network-based approaches achieve competitive sum-rate performance while significantly reducing computational complexity. GNN-based precoding, in particular, offers a strong trade-off between performance and scalability/efficiency. GNNs require lesser trainable parameters because of the distribution of weights in a structured manner (along the edges of a graph) and also employ a lesser number of multiplication operations than MLPs. We also analyzed the impact of imperfect CSIT and nonlinearities, such as power amplifier distortions, on precoding strategies. The results confirmed that neural network-based precoders maintain robustness under such conditions, outperforming conventional suboptimal schemes like Zero-Forcing (ZF). In particular, the incorporation of the non-linear knowledge into the self-supervised training stage allows MLP and GNN to achieve higher system capacity than ZF and does not show saturation behavior in the high-SNR regime as in the WMMSE benchmark. GNN records slightly higher system capacity than MLP for both underloaded and critically-loaded scenarios. Moreover, our radiation pattern analysis highlighted how different learning-based policies allocate power among common and private streams. Unlike WMMSE, the neural network-based precoding policies exhibit higher common rates.

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